

THE TEACHER AND CHANGES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

While considering all the changes that are happening in society and science, the role and personality of the teacher is not left untouched. The teacher role isn't only to teach or to lecture but they also have a motivational and encouraging role for pupil`s, to be a good manager, strategist and a ideator of different new innovation. They should be the submitters of the question, the questions that will encourage pupils to think and being logic. The modern teacher builds the concept of teaching in the function of achieving educational results and guides the teaching according to the pupil`s needs and interests.

Keywords: teacher, education, changes in education, teaching, knowledge

1. Introduction

A good teacher, creates a teaching environment that encourages pupil`s to teach how to learn, they are given clear instructions and continuous information whenever the pupil`s need it. A good teacher, through encouragement, helps the development of various interests and creative ability. The duty of the teacher is not by ordering pupil`s to learn, but is the role of encourager and helper for pupil`s in the process of learning.

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While in the past the teacher was a leader in the educational process and taught teaching in the teaching or factual content, he was a provider of information for the pupils, the controller, the orderer, the person who knew everything and had the authoritarian position in the classroom.

Regarding the stated above the pupils were receivers of pre-made information and as a result of this form of education, the pupil was a reproducer, learning only to get a passing grades, most of them were passive in the process of learning and they would agree with all the information and the way that it was given to them.

2. Teaching, teacher, education

The new concept of teaching, in which the profile of the modern teacher is reflected, orients the teaching in the standards and results of learning, where the role of the teacher is a coordinator, advisor, stimulator, instructor and guider in the teaching process.

The elements on the basis of which we evaluate the productivity of the teacher's work are these:

- Have oral communication skills and appropriate way of communicating with pupil's
- Possessing skills to implement teaching methods and tools, selecting and adapting them to a learning situation,
- Have the ability to transmit knowledge clearly, vividly and freely
- Skill for creative and inspirational teaching work
- Courage and determination to carry out the duty and the function of the teacher
- Possessing skills to develop ideas and to be flexible in working with pupil's
- Have adequate preparation to undertake the learning and school engagements
- Possessing cooperative skills in partnership with other subjects (teachers, directors, parents, associates, etc. (Murati, X. H., 2002).

By organizing the work or the teaching process we understand the recognition and reflection of the didactic-methodical teaching procedure and the determination of the pathways for realization of the contents and purposes of the lesson, the means and methods of raising the scientific level of learning, the essence and the most important factors determining success and efficiency of teaching. (Murati, X. H., 2002).

The structure of each lesson should be determined by the teacher, based on situations due to objective and subjective circumstances, which follow the educational-learning work in the classroom.

- Educational purpose of the teaching unit;
- The volume of the learning unit (the explanation of that learning unit can last 15 minutes up to 30 minutes);
- Application and interaction of teaching methods and forms;
- Providing teaching materials and didactic materials and the duration of their use;

- The range of choice and solution of the examples and the degree of their complexity;
- How to self-control pupils' knowledge, skills and expressions etc. (Jaka, B., 1998, fq.147)

The pupil in the learning process acquires knowledge, skills and expression, through teaching he is educated and taught, after all the lesson is organized for him. But the pupil in this work is not passive and isolated, but he is subject to influence on him, but also affects himself on two other learning factors, on matter and on the teacher. The material should revive the pupil's interest, activate it, while under its influence the pupil changes; he becomes aware of the new knowledge and works in improving the quality of previous knowledge. Knowledge also affects the emotional sphere of pupil's personality. Each pupil learns the material in a specific perspective, in a personal and specific way, which primarily depends on the intellectual psychological abilities of the pupil and from the extensive and intense aspect of the prior knowledge.

The teacher as an important factor in the realization of educational work is analyzed in several dimensions, and from the dimensions of his professional development in fact towards the individual change as a professional and educational protagonist and in the dimension of changing the school as an institution of organized education. This has revealed that our problems or attention focuses on: the teacher as a personality, the attitude of the teacher to the pupil's, the style and the way of working, the strategies and methodology of the teaching work that the teacher will use or select in his learning-education.... Therefore his professional and moral preparation must also be at a level of satisfaction so that he can successfully accomplish his job. If we look at the development of the school and the role of the teacher in the historical aspect, we will notice that the function but also the role of the teacher has changed as the society has changed, together with the school's functioning. (Murati, R., 2016, faq.85).

When talking about reforms or changes in education we need to consider some key elements or key points as follows:

- a) Given the fact that issues and concerns about the education have an interdisciplinary character, first of all should be done analysis of the achievements in education but not only here, but also in other educational-scientific disciplines that relate to educational and teaching issues
- b) There should be comparisons of learning and education in our country and in other developed countries.
- c) The social, cultural, political, ethnic positioning and socio-economic position or factor should be studied and reviewed, in order to discover the current situation or position where we are, what to change, and where we want to reach or what we want to achieve with the relevant changes.
- d) Always before making a substantial step for change, teachers should first be informed and consulted as the main bearer of the educational process, on the character and importance of the changes we want to implement, and the next step is their training through seminars, courses and various trainings for their professional upgrading.

- e) Provide professional staff (experts) and sufficient material resources for successful implementation of change.
- f) Always take into consideration eventual problems that may arise during the course of the changes as well as possible failures during the realization of certain changes in education.

The revolutionary changes in society that are developing towards the democratization and humanism of our society determine the gradual change of school position in society, bring about radical changes in internal relations put the pupil's position in the process of more active and objective position in the educational process, affect the greatest affirmation of the humanistic values in which the whole life and work of the school is based. *"Under the scheme of pedagogical innovation studies at school, there are three main levels that form a continuous progress, such as assimilation, change, and transformation levels. Each level is assumed to be more advanced than the previous one."* (Mandiq, P., 1985).

The methodological dimensions for effective teaching and learning are numerous. It is important that teachers should constantly be in the role of the innovator of the learning process, experimenting and evaluating different methodological dimensions that can be applied in curricular areas or subject areas tailored to the interests and needs of pupil's.

3. Recommendations

In pedagogy and educational practice, the professional development is presented as a process and a very important aspect of modern teaching organization.

Our study is based on initial questions:

- 1) What qualitative changes have occurred in the development of profession of teachers?
- 2) What are the key factors that have influenced the need for development of teachers, teaching in the time of changes?

4. Conclusion

The development and professional changes of teachers and teaching process as a concept is broad and it includes extended elements inside the field of pedagogy, didactics, methodology, teaching and similar technology.

Practically this kind of development reclines on three pillars:

- Expansion, innovation and update of theoretical, scientific and professional knowledge acquired during formal or basic education;
- Transfer, exchange and promotion of advanced teaching experiences;
- Placement of a contemporary system in favor of methods, techniques and new interactive teaching methodologies.

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